

RADIOACTIVE ORGANIC BROMO COMPOUNDS.

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A few radioactive bromo compounds have been prepared and the yield of the radioactive materials in the compounds determined.

The use of artificially radioactive substances in botanical and biological investigations is increasing very rapidly. Hevesy and others (*Nature*, 1936, 137, 66; 1935, 136, 754) used radioactive phosphorus to trace the course of phosphorus in the body of plants and animals. Recently, attention has been drawn to the preparation of radioactive organic bromo compounds by Friedmann, Solomon and Werthessen (*Nature*, 1939, 143, 472) and they propose to use them in biological experiments. An account of some of our experiments along similar lines is described below.

The radioactive isotope Br^{80} has been chosen by us because it has a conveniently long half-life (4.2 hours) and is chemically reactive. The large water-sensitivity of the radioactive isotope further facilitates our experiments with a comparatively weak Ra-Be source. The relative abundance of Br^{79} in natural bromine is also high, being about 51.4 %.

The first technique is the addition of bromine to a double bond. Bromine was introduced to the unsaturated double bond of oleic acid according to the following representation :

Ethylene dibromide (10g.) was irradiated with slow neutrons from a 60 mc (Ra-Be) source and after irradiation 2.9 g. of bromine were added. Oleic acid (5 g.) was next added slowly with shaking, and ethylene dibromide was distilled off in vacuum. The residue was taken in a thin-walled glass vessel and measurements were made with a thin walled Geiger-Müller counter. The method yielded a high concentration of radioactive material.

In the next reaction studied, bromine was introduced into the benzene ring. Thus, anisole was treated with bromine when bromoanisole was formed.

Anisole (5 g.) was dissolved in ethylene dibromide (100 g.). Bromine (3g.) was then added under cooling and constant shaking. When the characteristic colour of bromine just disappeared, ice-cold water was poured into the solution. Thus hydrobromic acid remains dissolved in water and the other layer containing ethylene dibromide and bromo-anisole was separated by a separating funnel. Traces of organic compound were removed from the aqueous layer by shaking with benzene. Hydrobromic acid was precipitated by silver nitrate and the activity of silver nitrate was measured.

The combined benzene and ethylene dibromide solution was thoroughly washed with dilute alkali to remove hydrobromic acid completely and then washed with water. It was then fractionally distilled, the fraction boiling at 223° being collected and used for the measurement of radioactivity.

It was found that almost equal activity appeared in silver bromide precipitate and bromoanisole solution. The concentration of radioactive material was found to be lower than in the first reaction.

In the next reaction studied acetanilide was treated with bromine when bromoacetanilide was formed and hydrobromic acid liberated.

Acetanilide (5g.) was added to 100 c.c. of irradiated ethylene dibromide and 7 g. of bromine were added with cooling. Shining crystals of *p*-bromoacetanilide at once separated out. They were filtered and recrystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 131°. The yield of radioactive material was of the same order as that obtained in the case of bromoanisole.

Table I.

Relative radioactivity per g. atom of bromine.

Ethylene dibromide	1'0
Dibromo-oleic acid	32'5
Bromoanisole	8'7
<i>Para</i> -Bromo-acetanilide	6'5

It may be emphasised, however, that although care was taken to keep the geometry constant, the results can only be taken as qualitative.

A new method for introducing radioactive halogen into organic halides is that of Brejneva, Roginsky and Schilinsky (*Acta Physicochemica*, 1936, 5, 549). They used radioactive aluminium bromide, well known as a halogenation catalyst, and suggested an exchange between the aluminium and alkyl bromides and, therefore, a method of preparing radioactive organic halides according to the reaction

where the starred element is the radioactive constituent.

Our preliminary investigation has shown that phosphorus tribromide is rapidly activated by exchange reactions with irradiated ethyl bromide, *i.e.*, when they are mixed together, the radioactive bromine rapidly distributes itself between them in a ratio of bromine content of these compounds. Now, when an alcohol is treated with this activated phosphorus tribromide, the bromine atoms are quickly incorporated in it forming corresponding radioactive alkyl bromide. A typical experimental result is given :

Ethyl bromide (75 g.) was irradiated with slow neutrons. Phosphorus tribromide (2 g.) was shaken with irradiated ethyl bromide for about 15 minutes. Ethyl bromide was then distilled off from a water-bath. The activity of phosphorus tribromide was measured. Next, 12 g. of *isoamyl* alcohol were slowly added to phosphorus tribromide in benzene medium and the container was kept immersed in an ice-bath for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and the mixture refluxed for about 15 minutes. Ice and water were then added to the solution so that the excess of phosphorus tribromide broke up into phosphoric acid etc. which were washed up with dilute alkaline bicarbonate solution and water. The alkyl bromide was separated and dried by calcium chloride.

Measurements showed that about 65 % of the activity of phosphorus tribromide had been transferred to the alkyl bromide molecule.

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